

**The Pastoral
Counsellors**

JOURNAL OF NIGERIAN ASSOCIATION OF PASTORAL COUNSELLORS

In Collaboration With

Department of Religious and Intercultural Studies

and

Department of Guidance and Counselling
Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria

Volume 4 January 2025

ISSN: Print 2971-5199 Online 2971-5202

Editors in Chief

Prof Samson FATOKUN
Prof Donald ODELEYE

Managing Editors

Prof Isaiah ABOLARIN
Assoc. Prof Adekunle OTUNLA
Dr. Olabisi Precious T. KILLIAN
Dr. Tayo ADEYANJU

Corresponding Editor

Dr. Adebayo Ola AFOLARANMI

Leveraging Artificial Intelligence to Enhance Evangelism and Facilitate Planting in Emerging Communities

Adebunmi Olaide POPOOLA

Department of Arts and Social Sciences Education, Lead City University, Ibadan
polizbee@gmail.com, +2348035348867, <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-2731-3645>

Monilola Dasola OYETADE, PhD

Department of Arts and Social Sciences Education, Lead City University, Ibadan
monioyetade2013@gmail.com, +2347057358476

Abstract

The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a tool for outreach and innovation, rather than just its roles and dynamic approach to the challenges and opportunities within new communities or environments cannot be over-emphasized. AI is rapidly transforming various sectors, and its potential to enhance evangelism and facilitate church planting in emerging communities is becoming increasingly evident. Therefore, this study explores the usefulness of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools in enhancing evangelism and facilitating church planting in new communities. The research aims to understand how AI can be leveraged to spread the religious messages, improve outreach efforts, engage communities, and improve building faith-based networks to support the establishment of new churches. This study also analyzes the effectiveness of various AI applications in evangelism and church growth. AI-driven tools, such as social media analytic, personalized messaging platforms, and virtual reality experiences, among others, can significantly enhance community engagement and evangelistic efforts. Specifically, AI tools were found to be beneficial to the reach of evangelistic messages, improve conversion rates, streamline the process of identifying potential church members and increase the level of welfare members enjoy from the church. Additionally, AI-assisted planning and resource management were crucial in reducing the time and cost of setting up new churches. The study concludes that AI can play a transformative role in modern evangelism and church planting, offering innovative solutions to reach and engage communities more effectively. These insights are valuable for church leaders and evangelists seeking to leverage technology to expand their missions and establish new spiritual communities in contemporary settings.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Evangelism, Church Planting, Community

Introduction

In the age of technology, church and other faith-based organisations also need to key into the global trend of digitization and tap into the numerous benefits that technology offers to progress and move with the trends which will eventually lead to its growth and multiplications, both spiritually and numerically. The intersection of faith and innovation presents a compelling frontier for spiritual growth. As communities become increasingly diverse and digitally connected, churches face the challenge of reaching individuals in new and creative ways. This paper explores using Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools to enhance evangelism and church planting.

Evangelism is from a Greek word εὐαγγέλιον (*euangelion*) which literally means 'good news'. In other words, it means reaching out to preach the good news of Jesus Christ to those who are yet to know Him and accept Him as their Lord and personal saviour. This is to fulfil the great commission of Jesus Christ in Matthew 28: 18 – 20 when He told His disciples and the believers to go after the lost souls. "Therefore go and make disciples of all nations, baptizing them in the name of the Father and of the Son and of the Holy Spirit, and teaching them to obey everything I have commanded you. And surely I am with you always, to the very end

of the age." Similarly, in Acts 1: 8, He says "But you will receive power when the Holy Spirit comes on you; and you will be my witnesses in Jerusalem, and in all Judea and Samaria, and to the ends of the earth" (New International Version). Thus, yielding to this clarion call of Salvation, Christians must establish churches to reach as many as possible for Christ. Artificial Intelligence (AI) one of the most significant technological advancements of the 21st Century, has the potential role in expanding the reach and the impact of evangelism, especially in the area of church planting.

Church planting is the process of establishing a church in a new community especially when the distance of an existing church is far from the people of the community, it could involve setting up the church in a rural area or a newly located community with the aim of making it an easily reached place of worship for people in the community. Church planting is often preceded by evangelism. As communities grow more diverse and digitally connected, traditional methods of spreading the Gospel and establishing new churches must adapt to remain relevant and effective.

AI offers divers opportunities to enhance these efforts, Copeland (2024) asserted that artificial intelligence (AI) refers to the ability of a digital computer or computer-controlled robot to perform tasks commonly associated with intelligent beings, he added that the term is frequently applied to the project of developing systems endowed with the intellectual processes characteristic of humans, such as the ability to reason, discover meaning, genius intelligence exhibited by machines, particularly computer systems. Also, Wikipedia Contributors (2024) defined AI as a field of research in computer science that develops and studies methods and software that enable machines to perceive their environment and use learning and intelligence to take actions that maximize their chances of achieving defined goals. Artificial intelligence (AI) is the theory and development of computer systems capable of performing tasks that historically required human intelligence, such as recognizing speech, making decisions, and identifying patterns. Coursera (2024) explained AI is an umbrella term that encompasses a wide variety of technologies, including machine learning, deep learning, and natural language processing (NLP). Tithe.ly (2018) emphasised that technology enables the mission of the church in the area of expansion; intelligent decision-making; radical collaboration; and in mobilized and equipped congregation. Ugboh (2023) opined that the church should also embrace technological innovation since it is open ended and not limited to a particular system because it is not an end by itself but it is a means to an end, so it cannot stand in isolation from other factors that supports it. Also, he stressed the fact that church require creative leaders who are agents of change which can provide enabling environment along with other human entities who are creative enough to respond appropriately to the move in order to foster sound change.

Hendricks, et. al (2022) noted that digital science and technology has become an effective method in fulfilling church missions in spite of the emergence of Covid-19 pandemic of 2019 and 2020 across globe. Fagunwa (2015) buttressed that christians in Nigeria reads online spiritual books frequently (for example, *Open Heaven Devotional* book written by Pastor E. A. Adebayo) which also serves as a means of evangelism to many worldwide. Thus, he underscores that technology in itself is neutral and should be encouraged in a way that will promote the growth of the church.

However, despite the potential benefits comes challenges. Many scholars are concern about the use of AI in religious contexts, especially in the area of privacy, authenticity, and the potential for technology depersonalize spiritual interactions. Even at that, this paper argues that when AI is used thoughtfully and ethically, it can become a powerful tool in advancing the mission of the church in terms of vibrancy and connectivity of faith communities in the digital era.

Theoretical Framework

The following theories can apply to use of Artificial Intelligence in today's church:

Social Learning Theory (Albert Bandura)

Modeling Behavior: AI can facilitate the creation of digital content (videos, blogs, podcasts) that showcases individuals engaging in evangelistic activities or living out their faith. This content serves as a model for others to observe and imitate others who are giving testimonies of their faiths. AI tools can be used as a means to investigate and understand ways that positive role models can be used to encourage desirable behaviours and to facilitate social change as related to the social learning theory of Albert Bandura.

Diffusion of Innovations (Everette Rogers)

Early Adoption and Communication: AI can identify potential "early adopters" within a community, those who are more open to new ideas and innovations in evangelism. By targeting these individuals with tailored messages and resources, churches can encourage them to embrace and spread new evangelistic practices using AI, thus facilitating the overall diffusion of these practices within the community.

Facilitating Information Flow: AI can enhance communication channels (e.g., chatbots, social media engagement) to efficiently disseminate information about church initiatives, events, and innovations in evangelism. By streamlining these processes, AI decreases the barriers to adoption and encourages broader community engagement. AI helps in facilitating the spread of new ideas and practices

Feedback and Adaptation: AI tools can gather feedback from community members regarding new evangelistic methods, allowing churches to adapt their strategies based on real-time data. This responsiveness can lead to a quicker diffusion of successful practices that resonate with the community's needs.

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

Basic Needs: To engage individuals effectively, churches can use AI to assess the community's basic needs such as food, safety, or social belonging. AI algorithms can identify individuals or families in need and the church can make provision for such needs as a means of winning souls for Christ.

Facilitating Self-Actualization: As individuals' basic needs are met, churches can leverage AI to create personalized faith journeys. AI can suggest resources, Bible studies, or mentorship opportunities that enrich the spiritual lives of congregants, helping them move toward self-actualization in their faith.

Types of Artificial Intelligence Which Can Boost Evangelism and Church Planting

AI-driven tools that can be used for evangelism are Chat-bots, Natural Language Processing (NLP), AI-powered Bible Study (You version and Bible AI), Social Media AI Tools for Outreach, Hootsuite (Loomly, Sprout Social and Buffer, etc.), AI Content Creation, Virtual and Augmented Reality for Evangelism, Voice Assists for Faith-Based Content, AI-Driven Data Analytics for Church Growth. FaithGPT (2024) also analysed useful websites that can assist the church in evangelism, church planting and church growth including Ideogram.ai, Open.AI, Leonardo.ai, heygen.com, descript.com, wordly.ai among others

The Roles of Artificial Intelligence in Promoting Evangelism and Church Planting

Scoggins (2024), explains practical ways for churches to benefit from AI as these:

Sermons

AI-based content generation tools like ChatGPT, Frase or Headline can be used to suggest catching titles for sermons to generate stories and illustrations to make sermons interesting. Research and Scripture cross-reference materials like Logos Bible software or Bible Hubs can help pastors find relevant verses quickly while preparing for evangelism outreach or sermons. AI tools like Otter.ai or Rev.ai can also be used to generate written sermons or messages.

Content

AI-powered tools can be used to generate social media posts of church activities, sermons, and inspirational quotes. They can also be used to generate and proofread content for church newsletters. These tools include Article Forge or conversion.ai. ChatGPT can also be used for devotional bible readings, bible reading plans, and illustrations to aid the effective growth of a church.

Artwork

Tools like Midjourney, Adobe Photoshop or Canvas can be used to generate sermon artwork, social media artwork, and Kids Ministry Artwork (Artbreeder or DeepArt.io) to customize artwork and automated images.

Website

ChatGPT can write code and scripts, it can create artwork, photos, and more for the church website. AI platforms like OpenAI's Codex or DeepCode can assist with generating code snippets or providing coding suggestions for website development. AI automation tools like Zapier or Integromat can help automate specialized tasks, like sending email notifications, updating databases, or integrating with other web services. Chatbot platforms like Chatfuel or Dialogflow can also be used to create AI-powered chatbots that handle routine tasks, provide information, or direct inquiries until a human response is available.

Video Editing

AI tools can be used for editing sermons: AI video editing tools like Magisto or Adobe Premiere Pro can automate tasks such as trimming, transitions, and captioning, making the sermon editing process more efficient. Likewise, Sermon Clipping AI tools like Video Indexer by Microsoft Azure or Google Cloud Video Intelligence can assist in automatically segmenting and indexing sermon videos based on keywords or specific topics.

Furthermore, the benefits of AI in promoting the gospels are further analysed by Earls (2023), Jeff (2023), Shariat (2023), Legacy Church (2024) and Christianity Today (2023) as:

1. ***It can be used as an evangelistic tool to spread the gospel to others.*** With AI-powered chatbots and virtual assistants, it is possible to create interactive experiences that can engage people in conversations about faith, answer their questions, and provide resources for learning and exploration.
2. ***It can reach a wider audience than traditional forms of evangelism, such as in-person events or door-to-door visits.*** AI could also be used to create personalized evangelistic experiences, tailoring the message and content to the individual needs and interests of each user. This could help make evangelism more relevant and engaging to people, increasing the chances of conversion.
3. ***AI also makes it easier for churches to host and run successful online meetings, conferences, or Bible studies without the need for physical spaces.*** By using AI tools such as digital whiteboards and video conferencing platforms, churches can save time and money while providing an engaging environment for members to engage in discussion and fellowship.
4. ***Pastoral counselling and support.*** ChatGPT could potentially be used to provide pastoral counselling and support to members of the congregation who may be struggling with personal or spiritual issues. By interacting with ChatGPT, individuals could receive guidance, encouragement, and advice that is grounded in biblical teachings and pastoral wisdom.
5. ***Strengthening Community Engagement.*** AI-powered communication tools offer churches the opportunity to strengthen community engagement and foster meaningful connections among members. Chatbots and virtual assistants can provide real-time support and information, answer

frequently asked questions, and facilitate online prayer requests and pastoral care. Additionally, AI-driven analytics can help church leaders gain valuable insights into community demographics, preferences, and engagement patterns, enabling them to adapt and refine their outreach strategies effectively.

6. ***It Improves Administrative Efficiency.*** From managing church finances to coordinating volunteer schedules, administrative tasks can often consume valuable time and resources that could be better allocated to ministry and service. AI-driven solutions streamline administrative workflows by automating routine tasks, optimizing resource allocation, and providing actionable insights for informed decision-making. By harnessing the power of AI, churches can operate more efficiently and effectively, freeing up time and resources to focus on their core mission and ministry objectives.
7. ***It Enhances the Worship Experience.*** AI-powered tools can facilitate dynamic worship services through intelligent lighting and sound systems, immersive multimedia presentations, and even AI-generated music compositions. These technologies create an atmosphere of reverence and awe, fostering deeper engagement and connection with the divine during worship gatherings.
8. ***It Personalizes Spiritual Growth.*** AI-driven platforms and applications can analyze individual spiritual needs, preferences, and learning styles to provide tailored recommendations for Bible study, devotional resources, and theological insights. By leveraging machine learning algorithms, churches can empower congregants to deepen their understanding of scripture and grow in their relationship with God in personalized and meaningful ways.
9. ***Communication, Outreach, and Virtual Ministry Opportunities.*** While person-to-person contact will always be paramount, for ministries that span many borders, automated communication processes using AI-powered chatbots or virtual assistants can create interactive experiences that engage people in conversations about faith, answer their questions, and provide personalized resources for discipleship and prayer.
10. ***AI offers pastors the gift of time.*** The time spent creating sermon outlines in traditional ways can be invested in prayer, relationship building and congregational care. In just a few minutes, it can provide pages of information on the people of Thessalonica, compile every Bible verse on money and generosity, and then summarize and compare dissertations on allusions found in Job.

Conclusion

In an age characterized by rapid technological advancement, the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into the realms of evangelism and church planting presents a transformative opportunity for communities and faith-based organizations. AI offers unique tools to enhance outreach efforts, streamline communication, and personalize engagement with potential congregants. AI-driven platforms can identify community needs and preferences, enabling churches to tailor their programs effectively and resonate more profoundly with diverse populations.

The effectiveness of AI in promoting evangelism is evident in its ability to analyze large datasets, allowing for informed decision-making and strategic planning. This capability can lead to the establishment of new churches and the sustainable growth of established congregations by fostering deeper connections within the community. Furthermore, AI's role in digital outreach, through social media engagement and targeted messaging, ensures that the transformative messages of faith reach beyond traditional boundaries, inviting individuals who may have previously felt disconnected.

However, it is crucial to conclude this paper further that the use of AI is not without challenges. Ethical considerations, such as maintaining genuine human connection and transparency in communication, must take precedence as churches navigate this digital landscape. Emphasizing the importance of human relationships in the faith community will ensure that technology serves to enhance, not replace the core

values of evangelism and pastoral care, and it does not rule out the space of the Holy Spirit inspiration and anointing in evangelism, church planting and church growth.

Recommendations

Therefore, AI is recommended to be very useful in propagating the gospel of Jesus Christ to the unreached. Using it is neither a sin nor neglect of the Holy Spirit so the Pastors, Evangelists and church planters should use the available AI tools within their reach. Also, AI tools that can assist in the video and audio creation of bible stories can be used by pastors in the rural areas for revivals, evangelisms and bible studies. Common AI contents like SMS, Whatsapp messages and other social media can be used to check the welfare of the worshippers and celebrate them on special occasions so as to promote love and oneness in the church. Pastors should not be statics in improving their knowledge about AI contents so as to reduce their stress and give them enough time to look after their own family affairs too.

References

- Christianity Today. (2023, November 1). 5 key ways AI can benefit pastors, even the skeptical ones. Retrieved October 22, 2024, from <https://www.christianitytoday.com>
- Christianity Today. (2023, November 1). 5 key ways AI can benefit pastors, even the skeptical ones. Retrieved October 22, 2024, from <https://www.christianitytoday.com>
- Copeland, B. (2024, October 20). Artificial intelligence. *Encyclopedia Britannica*. Retrieved October 21, 2024, from <https://www.britannica.com/technology/artificial-intelligence>
- Diaz, I. (2021). Considering the efficacy of digital technology as a means of evangelization in Christian religious education. *Religious Education*, 116(2), 187-200. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00344087.2021.1872001>
- Earls, A. (2023, February 20). Q&AI: How artificial intelligence says it can help pastors. *Lifeway Research*. Retrieved October 22, 2024, from <https://research.lifeway.com/2023/02/20/qai-how-artificial-intelligence-says-it-can-help-pastors/?sfw=pass1729569682>
- Fagunwa, O. (2015). Church growth and information communication technology: A case study of Nigeria and UK. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35275.82725>
- FaithGPT. (2024, October 8). 10 practical ways to use AI in your church (images, videos, music, and more). *FaithGPT | Bringing the Bible to Digital Life with A.I.* Retrieved October 22, 2024, from <https://www.faithgpt.io/blog/10-practical-ways-to-use-ai-in-your-church>
- GovTech. (2021, April 23). Understanding the four types of artificial intelligence. Retrieved October 21, 2024, from <https://www.govtech.com/computing/understanding-the-four-types-of-artificial-intelligence>
- Hendriks, A. C., Hendriks, A. L., & Najooan, J. C. (2022). Weather the storm: Evangelizing amidst the pandemic. *Jurnal Koinonia: Fakultas Filsafat Universitas Advent Indonesia*, 14(1), 72-85. <https://doi.org/10.35974/koinonia.v14i1.2880>
- LegacyChurch. (2024, June 8). Exploring the role of artificial intelligence in the church. *Legacy Church*. Retrieved October 22, 2024, from <https://legacycc.org/embracing-innovation-exploring-the-role-of-artificial-intelligence-in-the-church>
- Magazine*. Retrieved October 22, 2024, from <https://outreachmagazine.com/resources/78122-4-ways-to-effectively-use-ai-in-ministry.html>
- Opade, O. F. (2023). Perspectives on digital evangelism: Exploring the intersection of technology and faith. *African Journal of Christian Religious Thought*, 6(2), 15-24. <https://doi.org/10.52589/ajchrt-idap2p2m>
- Scoggins, C. (2024, July 17). Practical ways for churches to use AI. *Church Visuals*. Retrieved October 22, 2024, from <https://churchvisuals.com/article/practical-ways-for-churches-to-use-ai>
- Shariat, H. (2023, November 14). 4 ways to effectively use AI in ministry. *Outreach*
- Staff, Coursera. (2024, April 3). What is artificial intelligence? Definition, uses, and types. *Coursera*. Retrieved October 21, 2024, from <https://www.coursera.org/articles/what-is-artificial-intelligence>
- The Church Digital. (2024, May 30). How churches can use AI: Let's ask AI. Retrieved October 22, 2024, from <https://be.thechurch.digital/blog/how-churches-can-use-ai>

Tithe.ly Next. (n.d.). 4 ways technology enables the mission of the Church. Retrieved from <https://get.tithe.ly/blog/church-technology>

Ugboh, G. (2023). The church and technotheology: A paradigm shift of theology and theological practice to overcome technological disruptions. *Journal of Ethics in Entrepreneurship and Technology*, 3(2), 59-78. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jeet-02-2023-0004>

Wikipedia contributors. (2024, October 21). Artificial intelligence. *Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Artificial_intelligence&oldid=1251935545